

STUDY PREVALENCE AND MORPHOLOGY OF PASSALURUS AMBIGUOUS (RUDOLPHI 1819) FROM WILD RABBIT

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Abstract

There is a large range of nematode were found in domestic as well as wild rabbit. The occurrence of Passalurus ambiguous is very rare in domestic or pet rabbit but abundantly found in wild rabbit. Passalurus ambiguous belongs to oxiuridae family resides in caecum and large intestine of rabbit. These species are not pathogenic in adult but in heavy infection may lead in to enteritis complex of disease that occurred around weaning. In our study, material collected from various places of Vaijapur tehsil during monsoon season (June 2024 to September 2024), brought it in to the laboratory for processing and microscopic observation. We collected 53 samples, out of which 33 were positive for Helminthes infection which contains eggs, larvae and adult worms of helminths. Majority positive samples contain infection of nematode i.e. *Passalurus ambiguous*.

Keywords: Wild rabbit, Nematodes, Passalurus ambiguous etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

In India, six different species of wild rabbit existing but number of factors threatened the existence of wild animals. Gastrointestinal parasites **CAUSE** great threat to the wild rabbit *Lepus nigricollis* (Indian hare: Black naped hare) generally found in Indian subcontinent and some island. *Passalurus ambiguous* belongs to oxiuridae family resides in caecum and large intestine of rabbit. These groups of pinworm nematodes are having medical as well as veterinary importance and identification of such nematodes much depends on ordinary microscope. [1] (Vicente et al.1997). Very few efforts have been made to use scanning electron microscope or similar molecular based tools in the identification of oxyurid nematodes (pinworms) [2]. Current study was carried out to examine the identification of oxyurid nematodes (pinworms) in Vaijapur tehsil by using simple microscope, to identify this species with higher certainty and to determine its characteristic morphology, which may contribute valuable information to knowledge of the oxyurids.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area

Vaijapur is located at 19.920N74.730E and situated on the Narangi River in Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar District of Marathwada region of Maharashtra. Goyegaon, Bhaur, Ladgaon, Khambala, Pimpalgaon, Savkhed Ganga are different villages near to Godavari River 10-20 KM away from the Vaijapur.

Sample Collection

Samples (wet fecal material from field/ habitat) were collected randomly from study area and brought to laboratory as quickly as possible for microscopic investigation. The material was poured in to clean cavity blocks and inspected for the presence of helminths or pinworms infection. Nematodes were separated from fecal and wash thoroughly in saline and mounted temporarily on glass slides for morphological identification of species. The recovered worms were preserved in 70% ethanol for further examination. Identification was done using identification keys. (Skinker, 1931; Yamaguti, 1961; Hugot et al., 1982; Vicente et al., 1997; Petter & Quentin, 2009).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the course of project from June 2024 to September 2024, 53 fecal material samples were collected from different places i.e. Goyegaon, Bhaur, Ladgaon, Khambala, Pimpalgaon, Savkhed Ganga of Vaijapur taluka. 33 samples were positive for nematode infection and percentage prevalence is 62.26%.

Table 1 Prevalence

Months	Total Samples	Positive Samples	Negative samples	Prevalence percentage
June 2024	10	7	3	70%
July 2024	18	12	6	66.66%
Aug 2024	15	10	5	66.66%
Sept 2024	10	4	6	40%
Total	53	33	20	62.26%

Figure 1 Shows total number of samples examined and prevalence of helminth infections

4. MORPHOLOGICAL STUDY

Adult *Passalurus ambiguus* is a whitish in colour with finely pointed pin like tail, so it is also known as “pin worm”, Measured up to the 4-10 mm in length. Presence of typical oxyurid esophageal bulb is seen. Mouth is triangular, provided by four papillae and surrounded by three teeth. Male have long tail with highly narrow portion with spicule handle. Female have long tail. Eggs are ovoid, thin double walled, brownish in colour with slightly flattened wall on one side. It ranges in between 80-95 um in size

Figure 2 Wild Rabbit in farm at Goyegaon, Vaijapur tehsil

Figure 3 *Passalurus ambiguus* (Male) from wild rabbit in Vaijapur tehsil

Figure 4 Posterior portion of *Passalurus ambiguus*

Figure 5 *Passalurus ambiguus* showing Presence of typical oxyurid esophageal bulb

5. DISCUSSION

Passalurus ambiguus is found everywhere across world in domestic as well as wild rabbits, hares and rodents. Very few researchers work on this nematode, Skinker 1931, Hugot et al. 1982, Pinto et al. 2004 studied morphological features of adult and eggs of the *Passalurus ambiguus* which are in close resemblance with our reported species. Elhawaray 2009 and Ashmawy et al. 2010 reported 40% prevalence of *Passalurus ambiguus* in younger rabbits in Egypt which is less than that of our record 62. 26%. From Egypt, Nermean Moamen Hussein et al. 2021 reported 45% prevalence which is quit less than that of our study but morphological characters reported by them shows resemblance with our reported species. Dos Santos et al. (2017) reported triangular mouth, provided by four papillae and surrounded by three teeth, same structure also observed in our observation during morphology study [6]. The egg recorded by Sioutis Georgious et al. (2021) was ovoid, double walled and light brown shows very much similarity with our recorded eggs.

Conclusion

From above all report we concluded that the species recorded by us from wild rabbit is *Passalurus ambiguus* but prevalence of this is high in our study area in monsoon season

Ethical statement

All experiments are carried out without sacrificing live animals. Thus, ethical approval for animal experimentation was not required. Fecal collection was performed in non-invasive manner. No animal was sacrificed for purpose of study.

Conflict of interest

There is no any conflict of interest

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